

Energy efficiency ratio analysis of cooling systems in dry and humid climates

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Abstract: Heating, ventilation and air-conditioning, HVAC, systems account for 50% of the total final energy consumption in buildings. Directive 2010/31/EU established "to promote the improvement of the energy efficiency of buildings" as the main objective of the Energy Efficiency of Buildings Directive. According to this target, different sustainable solutions such as the use of efficient air-cooling systems or renewable energies sources are proposed in literature. Then, air-cooling technologies based on indirect evaporative cooling could be an interesting alternative to traditional air-cooling systems based on direct expansion unit in terms of energy efficiency. This research work was based on the experimental study of two innovative air-cooling systems in terms of Energy Efficiency Ratio, EER. These systems consisted of a dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DIEC, and a desiccant dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DW-DIEC. Different experimental tests were established to compare the EER values of the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems under different outdoor air conditions. The highest EER values for DIEC and DW-DIEC, 10.6 and 9.2 respectively, were achieved for the maximum value of outdoor air temperature, 40 °C, and the minimum value of outdoor air humidity ratio, 8 g kg⁻¹.

Keywords: Indirect evaporative cooling technology, desiccant system, energy efficiency, sustainable air-cooling solutions.

1. Introduction

Sustainable development and the achievement of competitive air-cooling systems were established as main objectives in Energy Performance of Building Directive [1]. According to the target of the energy use reduction, different solutions such as the modification of the building's thermal envelope [2], the use of efficient air-cooling systems [3,4] and the use of renewable energies are proposed [5]. In this way, air-cooling technologies based on indirect evaporative cooling could be an alternative to traditional air-cooling systems based on direct expansion unit in terms of energy performance.

The main objective of this research work was to evaluate experimentally the energy efficiency of two innovative air-cooling systems: a dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DIEC, and a desiccant dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DW-DIEC. The Energy Efficiency Ratio, EER, values for both air-cooling systems under different outdoor air conditions were analysed. These systems worked with 100% outdoor air and did not use oils or refrigerant gases.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the air-cooling systems

Two innovative air-cooling systems based on the indirect evaporative cooling technology were studied in terms of energy efficiency in this research work: (i) dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DIEC, and (ii) desiccant dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DW-DIEC, see Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively. These air-cooling systems were mainly composed of:

- A fan on the process air side, where a constant outdoor air flow rate of $5000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ entered.
- A gross 60% filter located before the heat exchanger in the DIEC system and before the desiccant wheel, DW, in the DW-DIEC system.
- The dew-point indirect evaporative cooler based on a counterflow plate heat exchanger.
- A fine filter, ePM1 65%, after the heat exchanger in both air-cooling systems.
- A desiccant wheel for the DW-DIEC system.

Figure 1. Schematic of DIEC system.

Figure 2. Schematic of DW-DIEC system.

In the DIEC system there was a single inlet air stream and three air states: outdoor air flow, OA, supply air flow, SA, and exhaust air flow, EA, see Figure 1. In the DW-DIEC system there were two inlet air streams and five air states, due to the desiccant wheel: two outdoor air flows, OA, a supply air flow, SA, and two exhaust air flows, EA, see Figure 2.

The DIEC system consisted of alternative wet and dry channels separate by thin plates. The outdoor air flow, or secondary air flow, was cooled in the wet channels by water evaporation, and it was exhausted as wet air. The supply air flow, or primary air flow, was supplied after being cooled without adding moisture. The DW-DIEC system consisted of a desiccant wheel, DW, which decreased the outdoor air stream humidity before entering the cooling process in the DIEC unit. The values of the main parameters of DW and DIEC system are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the air-cooling systems.

System	Parameter	Value	Unit
DIEC	Nominal cooling capacity	18	kW
DIEC	Nominal supply air flow	2880	m ³ h ⁻¹
DIEC	Maximum water consumption	44	l h ⁻¹
DW	Nominal dehumidification capacity	16	kg h ⁻¹
DW	Nominal inlet air flow	5000	m ³ h ⁻¹
DW	Water vapour adsorption capacity	> 40	%

2.2. Set of experimental tests

Several experimental tests were proposed to study the energy efficiency ratio of two air-cooling systems under different outdoor air conditions, dry and humid. The outdoor air temperature, T_{OA} , and the outdoor air humidity ratio, ω_{OA} , were considered as input parameters. The outdoor air temperature values were in a range of 30 to 40 °C and the outdoor air humidity ratio values were in a range of 8 to 13 g kg⁻¹ during the experimental tests. The supply air flow, \dot{V}_{SA} , value was set to the nominal value, 2880 m³ h⁻¹. This value was constant throughout the experimental study. In this way, energy performance index could be studied under conditions of the same outdoor air temperature and different outdoor air humidity ratio, and vice versa. A total of six experimental tests were performed, see Table 2.

Table 2. Experimental tests conditions for studying the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems.

Test	T_{OA} [°C]	ω_{OA} [g kg ⁻¹]	\dot{V}_{SA} [m ³ h ⁻¹]
N1	30	8	2880
N2	35	8	2880
N3	40	8	2880
N4	30	13	2880
N5	35	13	2880
N6	40	13	2880

2.3. Energy Efficiency Ratio index

These innovative and efficient air-cooling systems, DIEC and DW-DIEC, were evaluated in terms of Energy Efficiency Ratio, EER. The values of several response parameters were obtained to develop this study: supply air temperature, T_{SA} , and supply air humidity ratio, ω_{SA} .

Energy Efficiency Ratio was calculated according to the Equation 1:

$$EER = \frac{\dot{Q}_{cooling}}{\dot{W}} = \frac{\rho_{air} \cdot \dot{V}_{SA} \cdot (h_{OA} - h_{SA})}{\dot{W}}$$

Where ρ_{air} is air density [kg m⁻³], \dot{V}_{SA} is supply volumetric air flow [m³ s⁻¹], h_{OA} is outdoor air specific enthalpy [kJ kg⁻¹], h_{SA} is supply air specific enthalpy [kJ kg⁻¹], \dot{W} is the electrical power consumption of DIEC or DW-DIEC and $\dot{Q}_{cooling}$ is the cooling capacity of DIEC or DW-DIEC.

3. Results and Analysis

3.1. Experimental results

According to the experimental tests carried out in the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems, a summary of the T_{SA} , ω_{SA} and EER results for each test and air-cooling system is shown in Table 3. The ranges of the T_{SA} values obtained were established at 17.7 °C – 29.8 °C and 16.8 °C – 24.7 °C for

the DIEC system and the DW-DIEC system, respectively. It should be noted that high EER values were obtained both for the DIEC system, between 3.1 and 10.6, and for the DW-DIEC system, between 4.3 and 9.2. The highest values of T_{SA} were shown for the DIEC system, $T_{SA,DIEC}$, under high values of outdoor air humidity ratio, 13 g kg^{-1} , see tests N4, N5 and N6 in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of experimental tests results.

Test	$T_{SA,DIEC}$ [°C]	$T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$ [°C]	$\omega_{SA,DIEC}$ [g kg ⁻¹]	$\omega_{SA,DW-DIEC}$ [g kg ⁻¹]	EER_{DIEC} [-]	$EER_{DW-DIEC}$ [-]
N1	17.7	17.1	8.0	6.2	7.2	5.7
N2	18.5	16.8	8.0	5.9	9.1	7.7
N3	19.8	17.1	8.0	5.6	10.6	9.2
N4	27.6	20.5	13.0	10.5	3.1	4.3
N5	28.5	22.3	13.0	11.0	5.0	5.7
N6	29.8	24.7	13.0	11.4	6.5	6.7

The experimental analysis was based on the study of the influence of the outdoor air conditions, T_{OA} and ω_{OA} , on, firstly, supply air temperature, T_{SA} ; and then, on energy efficiency ratio, EER, for the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems.

3.2. Comparison of supply air conditions

The set of tests N1 to N3 was compared with the objective of obtaining the influence of the T_{OA} value on the response variable T_{SA} while the ω_{OA} value remained constant at 8 g kg^{-1} . For experimental tests N1 to N3, an increase of 1 °C in T_{OA} meant an increase of 0.2 °C in $T_{SA,DIEC}$ and an increase of 0.06 °C in $T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$. So, it can be observed that the DW-DIEC system had a higher cooling capacity than the DIEC system due to the operation of the desiccant wheel, DW.

The experimental tests N1 and N4 were selected to compare the T_{SA} value according to the influence of the ω_{OA} value, see Figure 3. Test N1 shown the lowest T_{SA} difference between the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems. However, test N4 shown the highest T_{SA} difference between both air-cooling systems. For test N1 the $T_{SA,DIEC}$ and the $T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$ values were 17.7 °C and 17.1 °C , respectively. These T_{SA} values were so similar for a ω_{OA} value of 8 g kg^{-1} , see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Experimental tests conditions in tests N1 and N4.

In contrast, for test N4, the $T_{SA,DIEC}$ value was 27.6 °C and the $T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$ value was 20.5 °C. These T_{SA} values differed by 7.1 °C for the highest value of ω_{OA} , 13 g kg⁻¹, see Figure 3. So, in general, both the DIEC system and the DW-DIEC system showed similar values of T_{SA} for dry weather conditions. However, the DW-DIEC system showed lower and more comfortable T_{SA} values than the DIEC system under humid weather conditions.

3.3. Comparison of Energy Efficiency Ratio values

The outdoor air conditions, T_{OA} and ω_{OA} , also had a high influence on the energy efficiency ratio, EER, values of the DIEC and DW-DIEC air-cooling systems, see Figure 4. It can be observed that the highest EER values for DIEC and DW-DIEC, 10.6 and 9.2 respectively, were reached for weather conditions of maximum T_{OA} , 40 °C, and minimum ω_{OA} , 8 g kg⁻¹. However, the lowest EER values for DIEC and DW-DIEC, 3.1 and 4.3 respectively, were reached for the minimum T_{OA} value, 30 °C, and the maximum ω_{OA} value, 13 g kg⁻¹, see Figure 4. So, the low T_{OA} value had a high influence on the EER value for DIEC and the high energy consumption of the desiccant wheel had a high influence on the EER value for DW-DIEC.

Regarding the EER trend, comparing the EER values of both air-cooling systems, EER for DIEC was higher than EER for DW-DIEC under dry weather conditions (tests N1 to N3). However, EER for DIEC was lower than EER for DW-DIEC under humid weather conditions (tests N4 to N6), see Figure 4. So, it can be observed that DIEC showed high energy efficiency values for dry climates and DW-DIEC showed high energy efficiency values for humid climates.

Figure 4. Trend of EER values for DIEC and DW-DIEC according to weather conditions.

4. Conclusions

An experimental study of two innovative air-cooling systems in terms of energy efficiency was carried out in this research work. These systems were based on the indirect evaporative cooling technology: (i) dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DIEC, and (ii) desiccant dew-point indirect evaporative cooler, DW-DIEC. Several experimental tests were established to obtain and analyse

the supply air temperature, T_{SA} , and Energy Efficiency Ratio, EER, values of the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems under different weather conditions.

Based on the results, the outdoor air temperature, T_{OA} , and the outdoor air humidity ratio, ω_{OA} , had a high influence on the T_{SA} and EER results for both air-cooling systems. The DIEC and DW-DIEC systems showed similar values of T_{SA} for dry weather conditions. However, the DW-DIEC system showed lower T_{SA} values for humid weather conditions. In addition, the highest EER values for DIEC and DW-DIEC, 10.6 and 9.2 respectively, were reached for weather conditions of maximum T_{OA} , 40 °C, and minimum ω_{OA} , 8 g kg⁻¹.

The present study may have practical applications for works related to the energy performance of efficient air-cooling systems: the highest EER values were obtained for DIEC under dry weather conditions and for DW-DIEC under humid weather conditions. In addition, both air-cooling systems showed four to five times higher energy efficiency than a traditional air-cooling system based on a direct expansion unit.

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